

Acknowledgement

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References

1. L. P. HAMMETT and A. DINGWILL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 2721; 1934, 56, 327; *Chem. Rev.*, 1935, 16, 67.
2. L. A. FLEKSER, L. P. HAMMETT and A. DINGWILL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 2103.
3. STRAUVE and RADEHAUSEN, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1930, 58, 239.
4. PHILLIPS, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1954, 31, 81.

Spectrophotometric Studies on Complex Formation of Tantalum(V) with 7-Nitro-8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-Sulphonic Acid

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THE colour reaction between tantalum(V) and 7-nitro-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid has been studied to determine the optimum condition for analytical use of this reagent.

Absorption spectra and the effect of pH :

Absorption spectra of the reagent alone and solutions containing tantalum(V) and the reagent 7-nitro-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (NHQSA) at different pH values exhibit maximum absorbance at 375 nm. The results obtained show that the pH range for maximum and constant absorbance is 6 to 7.

Beer's law and stability :

The Beer's law is obeyed within the 1 mg. to 5 mg. of tantalum(V) permillilitre range.

The formation constant K of 1 : 2 complex calculated by Job's method and Mole ratio method¹⁻⁵ is recorded in the Table 1.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANT OF TA(V)-NHQSA COMPLEX

Method	Log K
1. Mole ratio	8.03
2. Job's	7.93
Average = 7.98	

Estimation of tantalum(V) :

Several estimations of tantalum were made by the method described above. The average of five determinations with 3.50 mg. of tantalum(V) is 3.45 mg. which varies between 3.43 mg. and 3.51 mg. with 95% confidence limit.

Effect of diverse ions :

Synthetic solutions containing 10 ppm. of tantalum (V) and varying amounts of diverse ions were prepared at pH 6.5 and tantalum determined in their presence. The following ions, with amounts in ppm given in parentheses, did not cause more than $\pm 3\%$ difference in absorbance.

NO₃⁻ (350), Cl⁻ (15), Br⁻ (10), I⁻ (15), Thiocyanate (250), Oxalate (125), Ba⁺² (105), Al⁺³ (10), Tartarate (300), Fluoride (350), Mo(VI) (450), V(V) (375), W (400), U(VI) (425), and Nb(V) (500).

References

1. A. K. MUKHERJI and A. K. DEY, *Anal. Chem. Acta*, 1958, 18, 324.
2. A. K. MUKHERJI and A. K. DEY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chemistry*, 1958, 6, 314.
3. J. H. YOE and A. H. JONES, *Ind. Engg. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 11, 19.
4. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4488.
5. P. JOB, *Ann. Chem. (Paris)*, 1928, 10.

Condensation of Acetylacetone with Aldehydes

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AN attempt was made to condense acetylacetone with benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde, 5-bromo salicylaldehyde, *p*-hydroxy-benzaldehyde and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde. The main object of this investigation was to compare the reactivity of acetyl acetone with phenylacetic acid and its para halo substituted derivatives, in Knoevenagel's reaction. The condensation of phenylacetic acid and its *p*-chloro, *p*-bromo, *p*-iodo and *p*-fluoro derivatives has already been carried out in this laboratory¹⁻⁵. Another object of the investigation was to find out conditions in which maximum yields were obtained.

As the Knoevenagel's reaction involves carbanion addition to the carbonyl group of the aldehydes, any substance which yields a more stable carbanion will be more reactive. Phenylacetic acid as compared to acetylacetone is expected to give a more stable carbanion, because of the delocalisation of the negative charge over the benzene nucleus. Hence the yields obtained in the condensation of acetylacetone with different aldehydes should be lower than those obtained in the condensation of phenylacetic acid with the same aldehydes under similar conditions. This has been confirmed by comparing the yields obtained in the present investigation (Table 1) with those obtained in the condensation of phenylacetic acid with the same aldehydes^{2,3,6,7}.

Experimental

Condensation with benzaldehyde : Equimolecular amounts of acetylacetone and benzaldehyde were

TABLE I

S.No.	R	R ₁	R ₂	A : B	t	T	t ₁	yield%	Z
1	H	H	H	1 : 1	120	12	105	50	piperidine
2	H	H	H	1 :	140	6	105	70	piperidine
3	OCH ₃	H	H	1 : 1	120	12	89	91.5	piperidine
4	OCH ₃	H	H	1 : 1	140	6	89	79.2	piperidine
5	H	OH	H	1 : 1	140	12	195	54.4	piperidine
6	H	OH	H	1 : 1	160	12	195	45.4	piperidine
7	H	OH	H	1 : 1	160	6	195	50	(C ₂ H ₅) ₃ N + Ac ₂ O
8	NO ₂	H	H	1 : 1	140	6	189	60	piperidine
9	NO ₂	H	H	1 : 1	140	6	189	72	(C ₂ H ₅) ₃ N + Ac ₂ O
10	NO ₂	H	H	1 : 1	160	6	189	88	(C ₂ H ₅) ₃ N + Ac ₂ O
11	Cl	H	H	1 : 1	140	6	115	82.6	piperidine
12	H	OH	Br	1 : 1	140	12	220	46.6	piperidine
13	H	OH	Br	1 : 1	140	6	220	63.3	(C ₂ H ₅) ₃ N + Ac ₂ O

where A = Acetylacetone, B = Aldehydes, Z = Base, t = Temperature of oil bath in degree centigrade, T = Time in hours, t₁ = Melting point in degree centigrade.

heated under reflux at different temperatures viz., 120°, 140° and 160° for different durations of time viz., 6, 12 and 18 hrs in the presence of different bases viz., pyridine, piperidine, α-picoline, a mixture of pyridine and acetic anhydride and a mixture of triethylamine and acetic anhydride. The condensed product, so obtained was washed with ether and the residue was recrystallised with ethanol and was found to be 1,1-diacetyl-2-phenylethylene (m.p. 105°), (Found : C, 76.2; H, 6.1% C₁₂H₁₂O₂ requires : C, 76.5; and H, 6.3%).

Condensation with anisaldehyde : The condensed product was recrystallised with acetone and was found to be 1,1-diacetyl 2-(p-methoxyphenyl) ethylene (m.p. 89°) (Found : C, 71.1; H, 6.3% ; C₁₃H₁₄O₃ requires : C, 71.5; H, 6.4%).

Condensation with salicylaldehyde : The condensed product was recrystallised with acetone and was found to be 1,1-diacetyl 2-(o-hydroxyphenyl) ethylene (m.p. 195°) (Found : C, 70.1; H, 5.3% ; C₁₂H₁₂O₃ requires : C, 70.5; H, 5.8%).

Condensation with p-nitrobenzaldehyde ; The condensed product was recrystallised with acetone and was found to be 1,1-diacetyl 2-(p-nitrophenyl) ethylene m.p. 189° (Found ; N, 5.7% . C₁₂H₁₁NO₄ requires N, 6.0%).

Condensation with p-chlorobenzaldehyde : The condensed product was recrystallised with ethanol and was found to be 1,1-diacetyl 2-(p-chlorophenyl) ethylene m.p. 115° (Found Cl, 15.8% : C₁₂H₁₁O₂Cl requires Cl, 16.1%).

Condensation with 5-bromosalicylaldehyde : The condensed product was recrystallised with acetone and was found to be 1,1-diacetyl 2-(2'-hydroxy-5'-bromophenyl) ethylene m.p. 220° (Found : Br, 27.9% ; C₁₂H₁₁O₃Br requires : Br 28.2%).

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References

- VISHNU CHANDRA and V. B. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 433.
- VISHNU CHANDRA and V. B. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 496.
- VISHNU CHANDRA and V. B. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 44, 675.
- VISHNU CHANDRA and V. B. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 1102.
- VISHNU CHANDRA and V. B. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 395.
- R. N. SINGH and VISHNU CHANDRA, *Agra University Journal of Research Science*, 1952, 1, 153.
- BUCKLES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4973.